

Yield of Carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) as Influenced by NPK Fertilizer Rates and Inter-Row Spacing in Sudan Savanna Zone of Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Carrot is grown extensive in northern Nigeria for consumption and income generation. However, carrot production in the Sudan Savanna Zone of Nigeria is curbed with low yields as a result of inappropriate fertilizer scheduling and poor plant spacing. The aim was to determine the yield of carrot to NPK rates and inter-row spacing. Based on this, two field experiments were carried out during dry seasons at the Teaching and Research Farms of Abdullahi Fodio University of Science and Technology Aliero located at Jega. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. The treatments consisted of five NPK rates (0, 150, 300, 450, and 600 kg ha⁻¹) and four inter-row spacing levels (10, 15, 20, and 25 cm). Results showed that application of NPK fertilizer significantly ($p > 0.05$) enhanced yield parameters. The highest root yield (10.42 t ha⁻¹) was observed with the application of 600 kg NPK ha⁻¹; coupled with 10 cm inter-row spacing. The study concludes that the application of 600 kg ha⁻¹ combined with a 10 cm spacing is recommended for maximizing carrot yield in the Sudan Savanna Zone of Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Keywords: *Daucus carota*, Inter-row spacing, NPK fertilizer, Root yield, Sudan Savanna

1.0 Introduction

Carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) is a significant wet season vegetable crop belonging to the Apiaceae family, valued globally for its crisp texture, wide range colours, and high nutritional content, particularly its richness in beta-carotene, a precursor to vitamin A^{1,2}. World annual production of carrots and turnips is estimated at 42 million tons, with China being the largest producer³. In Nigeria, carrot production predominantly concentrated in cities in Northern region such as Zaria, Sokoto, Kano, and Jos. However, the average yield remains low at approximately 15 t ha⁻¹, a stark contrast to yields obtainable in advanced agricultural systems like the USA, which can reach up to (170 t ha⁻¹)⁴.

This low yield in Nigeria's Savanna regions could be attributed to several constraints, among which inadequate fertilizer application and inappropriate plant spacing are paramount⁵. Carrot is known to be

heavy feeder of nutrients, removing substantial amounts of nitrogen (100 kg N ha⁻¹), phosphorus (50 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹), and potassium (180 kg K₂O ha⁻¹) from the soil, making it highly sensitive to soil fertility and moisture regimes⁶. Judicious application of NPK fertilizers is crucial, as nitrogen promotes vegetative growth and carbohydrate synthesis, phosphorus stimulates root development and diameter, and potassium enhances root quality and sugar accumulation⁷. However, the optimal dose is critical, as excessive nitrogen can lead to issues like root splitting, thereby reducing marketable yield⁸.

Similarly, plant spacing is a critical agronomic factor that directly influences plant competition for light, moisture, and nutrients, thereby affecting both the size of individual roots and the overall yield per hectare^{9, 10}. Wider spacing often results in larger individual roots but may reduce yield per unit area due to lower plant population, whereas closer spacing increases plant population but can intensify

competition, potentially leading to smaller roots¹¹.¹². Therefore, establishing an optimum plant population density is essential for maximizing carrot yield.

Several studies have investigated the effects of NPK rates and spacing on carrot growth in many regions. For instance,¹³ recommended 250 kg ha⁻¹ and 200 kg ha⁻¹ NPK at Sudan savanna ecology of Zaria, Kaduna, Nigeria, while Kharsan¹⁴ reported better performance with wider spacing at Madhya, Pradesh, India. Agronomic recommendations are highly specific to local soil, climate, and varieties¹⁵. There is a discernible lack of conclusive research defining the precise NPK fertilizer requirements and optimal plant spacing for carrot production within the specific context of the Sudan Savannah Zone of Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Therefore, this study was conducted to bridge this knowledge gap to determine the yield of carrot as influenced by NPK rates and spacing.

2.0. Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of the Study Area

The study was carried out during the 2023/2024 and 2024/2025 at two locations; the Fadama Teaching and Research Farm, Jega (Lat. 12° 12.99 N; Long. 4° 21.90E; 197m above sea level) and the University orchard at Abdullahi Fodio University of Science and Technology, Aliero (lat. 12°18.64'N; long. 4°29.85'E; 262 above sea level). Both sites are within the Sudan Savanna Agro-ecological Zone of Nigeria. The climate is characterized by an average annual rainfall of 550-700mm and temperatures ranging from 27°C to 41°C.¹⁶.

2.2 Soil Sampling and Analysis

Before the experimental trial, soil samples were collected from each plot (60 plots of 1.5 by 1 m) for both locations using simple random sampling from 0-30cm soil¹⁷ depth in 2023 and 2024 dry season. Thereafter, the composite samples were air-dried, large clods crushed, and soil sieved to pass through 2mm sieve. The samples were analyzed for physiochemical properties, texture, total Nitrogen, Phosphorous, Potassium, Cation Exchange Capacity and P^H. Nitrogen was determined by Macro – Kjeldhal method¹⁸, available Phosphorus by Bra-1 and available potassium by the use of NH₄OAC soil extract. Organic matter was determined by Walkley and Black methods as described by Weil and Brady

¹⁷, exchangeable Cations by acetic acid method¹⁹. Cations exchange capacity (CEC) were determined by ammonium saturation method as described by Chapman²⁰ and P^H was determined by the use of glass electrode digital pH meter in a 1:2 soil water mixture as recommended by Alberta Provincial Laboratory²¹, and soil texture by Hydrometer method as described by Rhodes²²

2.3. Source of Planting Material

The carrot seed CAROTTE TOUCHON (ALHERI NOMA) variety was sourced from the National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT) Bagauda Substation, Kano state.

2.4. Experimental Design and Treatments

The treatments consisted of five levels of NPK (15:15:15) fertilizer viz (0 kg⁻¹, 150 kg⁻¹, 300 kg⁻¹, 450 kg⁻¹, 600 kg⁻¹) and four inter row spacing (10cm, 15cm, 20cm, 25cm) which was arranged in Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with 3 replications²³.

2.5 Agronomic Practices

2.5.1 Land Preparation and planting

The experimental area was harrowed to a fine tilt and the land was then marked into plots and replications. A border space of 0.5m between plots and 1m between replicates were also marked.

2.5.2 Sowing

Carrot seed was sown at depth of 1cm using drilling method. The spacing was done on treatments basis (10cm, 15cm, 20cm, and 25cm).

2.5.3 Water application

Water channels were constructed for effective supply of water to each furrow during irrigation. The water was applied to the field at an interval of five days as recommended by⁷.

2.5.4 Weeding

Weeding was done manually with hoe at 3 and 5 weeks after sowing.

2.5.5 Fertilizer application

NPK (15:15:15) fertilizer was applied on treatment basis (0 kg⁻¹, 150 kg ha⁻¹, 300 kg ha⁻¹, 450 kg ha⁻¹, 600 kg ha⁻¹).

2.5.6 Pests control

Pests and diseases were controlled with appropriate/recommended phyto-sanitary measures (regular weeding, removal of infected plant (rogueing), and regular spraying of cypermerthrin plus dimethoate at rate of 1.0L ha⁻¹).

2.5.7 Harvesting

The roots were harvested by carefully hand pulling it from the soil at 90 days after the foliage have turned pale yellow¹.

2.6 Data collection

2.6.1. Length of root per plant (cm)

Five plant roots were randomly selected from each plot at harvest, after which the length of the roots were measured using a meter rule. The root lengths of the five plants were added and divided by five to obtain average.

2.6.2 Diameter of root per plant (cm)

The diameters of the five randomly selected plant roots were measured using a vernier caliper after which the diameter values were added and then divided by five for the mean diameter.

2.6.3. Root dry weight (g)

This was achieved by selecting five roots at random at harvest for oven drying at (70°C) to a constant weight and thereafter weighed using a mettler Toledo SB 16001 model and the means were recorded in grams.

2.6.4. Total yield per plot (kg)

Roots from the net plot were weighed using a mettler Toledo SB 16001 balance and the mean was recorded.

2.6.5. Total yield per hectare (Tons)

The harvested roots from each net plot were cleaned and weighed for each treatment plot using a mettler Toledo SB 16001 balance and expressed in tons per hectare.

2.6.6. Harvest index

This was calculated as a ratio of economic (root) yield to biological (total biomass) yield as shown in equation 1.

$$HI = \frac{\text{Root yield plot}^1}{\text{Biological yield plot}^1} - 1$$

2.7 Data Analysis

The data collected was subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using SAS software package. Treatments means were separated using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT).

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Soil Physical and Chemical Properties of the experimental Sites

Physical and chemical properties of soils in the study locations prior to the experiments are presented in Table 1. The result revealed that soil of Aliero has a pH of (6.45), for Jega is (6.11) which means that both sites fall under slightly acidic condition, which is good for plant growth. Organic matter of the two locations stood at (0.31) for Aliero and (2.0) for Jega. This indicates that soil of Jega is richer and holds water and nutrients more effectively. Both locations have similar total N, P, which were generally lower as described by Esu (1991 and 2004)²⁴, <0.1gkg⁻¹ indicate lower N, 0.1-0.2kg⁻¹ medium, and >0.2kg⁻¹ high. While P <10mgkg⁻¹ indicate low, 10-20mgkg⁻¹ moderate, and >20mgkg⁻¹ high. Ca and Mg were also low at both locations though slightly higher at Jega based on ratings by Esu (1991)²⁴, <2molkg⁻¹ indicate low Ca, 2-5cmolkg⁻¹ medium, and >5cmolkg⁻¹ high. While for Mg, <0.3cmolkg⁻¹ indicates low, 0.3-1.0cmolkg⁻¹ medium, and >1.0cmolkg⁻¹ indicate high. Potassium levels were good and virtually same at both locations. For CEC, soils of Aliero indicated low (5.99) while that of Jega indicated medium (8.94) as described by²⁴ (CEC <6 cmolkg⁻¹ is low, 6-12 medium, and >12 cmolkg⁻¹ is high). For soil physical properties, both soils were classified as sandy-loam with high sand percentage, moderate silt and low clay.

Table 1: Physical and Chemical properties of soil of the two experimental sites for Aliero and Jega during 2024 and 2025 dry season.

	Aliero	Jega
Particle size analysis	0-30cm depth	
Chemical Properties		
p ^H	6.45	6.11
Organic carbon %	0.18	0.87
Organic Matter %	0.31	2.0
Total N %	0.08	0.09
P mg/kg	0.95	1.05
Ca (Cmol/kg	0.60	0.78
Mg Cmol/kg	0.90	0.74
K Cmol/kg	2.58	2.56
CEC Cmol/kg	5.99	8.94
Physical properties		
Sand (%)	65.5	61.7
Silt (%)	25.8	28.2
Clay (%)	11.9	10.1

3.2 Root length (cm)

The effects of NPK rates and inter-row spacing on root length at Aliero and Jega is presented in Table 2. The result showed no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) amongst different NPK rates and inter-row spacing (Aliero). At Jega, result showed a significant difference amongst different NPK rates while inter-row spacing effect showed no significant difference. The longest root was observed in 600kg NPK rate while the shortest was observed in the control. The interaction between NPK rates and inter-row spacing on root length was not significant.

3.3 Root Diameter (cm)

The effects of NPK rates and inter-row spacing on root diameter at Aliero and Jega are presented in Table 2. The result showed a significant difference among different NPK rates while inter-row spacing effect showed no significant difference (Aliero). The highest value of root diameter was observed in 450kg NPK rates which was at par with 300kg and 600kg while the least was observed in the control (Aliero). At Jega, the effect of different NPK rates on root diameter showed no significant difference

while there was significant difference under inter-row spacing. The highest mean value was observed in plants spaced at 20cm which was at par with 15cm while the least was observed in 25cm spacing. The interaction between NPK rates and inter-row Spacing on root diameter was not significant.

3.4 Root Dry Weight (g)

The effects of NPK rates and inter-row spacing on root dry weight at Aliero and Jega is presented in Table 2. The result showed a significant difference among different NPK rates while inter-row spacing effect showed no significant difference (Aliero). The highest root dry weight was observed in 450kg NPK rate while the least was observed in the control (Aliero). On the other hand at Jega, there was no significant difference amongst different NPK rates while there was a significant difference amongst different inter-row spacing. The highest root dry weight was observed in plants spaced at 15cm while the least was observed in 10cm spacing. The interaction between NPK rates and inter-row spacing on root dry weight was not significant.

Table 2: Effects of NPK rates and inter-row Spacing on Root length, Root diameter, and Root dry weight of Carrot at Jega and Aliero locations.

Treatments	Root length (cm)		Root diameter (cm)		Root dry weight (kg)	
	Aliero 2023/2024	Jega 2024/2025	Aliero 2023/2024	Jega 2024/2025	Aliero 2023/2024	Jega 2024/2025
Fertilizer (kg ha⁻¹)						
0	9.32	6.60c	1.38b	2.35b	2.22cc	11.15b
150	10.40	8.42bb	1.62bb	3.37a	4.52bc	17.40a
300	11.27	8.60bb	1.94a	3.34a	6.25ab	18.44a
450	11.27	8.84ab	2.17a	3.46a	7.20a	18.88a
600	11.20	9.58a	1.95a	3.53a	6.00ab	18.09a
SE±	1.680	0.290	0.039	0.164	2.381	1.544
Inter-row Spacing (cm)						
10	8.40b	8.42	1.48b	2.92bb	4.68	14.06b
15	12.53a	8.15	1.88a	3.28ab	5.52	19.50a
20	11.00a	8.66	1.96a	3.75a	5.86	16.24ab
25	10.84a	8.42	1.92a	2.89b	4.89	17.36ab
SE±	1.502	0.259	0.035	0.147	2.129	1.381
Interaction						
FxS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Means followed by the same letter (s) within a treatment group are not significantly different at 5% level of significance difference using DMRT. * = Significant at 5%, NS = Not significant, WAP = Weeks after Planting.

3.5 Yield (t ha⁻¹)

The effects of NPK rates and inter-row spacing on yield at Aliero and Jega is presented in Table 3. The result showed that there was a significant difference at both Aliero and Jega under different NPK rates. The highest root yield was observed in 600kg NPK rate which was statistically the same with 150kg NPK rates while the lowest root yield was observed in the control (Aliero). Similarly at Jega, the highest root yield was observed in 600kg NPK rate while the least was observed in the control. On the other hand, there was no significant difference amongst different inter-row spacing on yield at Aliero while there was significant difference at Jega. Plant spaced at 10cm gave the highest yield which was statistically similar to plant spaced at 25cm while the least was observed in plant spaced at 20cm

spacing. The interaction between the two factors was not significant.

3.6 Harvest Index

The effect of NPK rates and inter-row spacing on harvest index at Aliero and Jega are presented in Table 3. The result showed a significant difference under different NPK rates at Aliero only while there was no significant difference at Jega. The highest harvest index value was observed in 150kg NPK rate which was statistically similar to 600kg, and 450kg while the least was observed in the control (Aliero). On the other hand, the effect of different inter-row spacing on harvest index was not significant at both Aliero and Jega. The interaction between NPK rates and Spacing was also not significant.

Table 3: Effects of NPK rates and inter-row Spacing on Yield and Harvest index of Carrot at Jega and Aliero locations.

Treatments	Yield per hectare (t ha ⁻¹)		Harvest Index (%)	
	Aliero 2023/2024	Jega 2024/2025	Aliero 2023/2024	Jega 2024/2025
Fertilizer (kg ha⁻¹)				
0	2.81b	2.25c	0.44b	0.55
150	6.54a	9.42b	0.54a	0.56
300	5.51ab	9.85b	0.51ab	0.54
450	5.27ab	9.56b	0.48ab	0.54
600	6.56a	12.90a	0.53ab	0.57
SE±	1.008	1.004	0.030	0.015
Inter-row Spacing (cm)				
10	6.04	10.42a	0.49	0.53
15	6.32	8.66ab	0.53	0.56
20	4.83	6.58b	0.48	0.54
25	4.16	9.53a	0.51	0.56
SE±	0.903	0.898	0.027	0.013
Interaction				
FxS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Means followed by the same letter (s) within a treatment group are not significantly different at 5% level of significance difference using DMRT. * = Significant at 5%, NS = Not significant, WAP = Weeks after Planting.

4 Discussion

Under yield attributes, root parameters (length, diameter, and dry weight) responded positively to fertilizer application. At Aliero, 450 kg ha⁻¹ produced significantly higher root diameter (2.17cm) and dry weight (7.20g), consistent with²⁵, who observed significant improvements in root morphology of radish with increased nitrogen and phosphorous. Similarly,¹² reported that optimum potato tuber yield was achieved with site specific NPK management, emphasizing the importance of adequate fertilization. At both Aliero and Jega, the control plot (0 kg ha⁻¹) gave significantly lesser yield than the treated plots. This could be as a result of the nature of Sudan Savanna soils that has inherent low nutrient as highlighted by⁵. The highest yields were observed at 600kg ha⁻¹ application at both locations with Jega showing a more pronounced effect (12.90tha⁻¹). This finding conforms to the finding of^{7,21}, who recommended high application rates (200-250kg ha⁻¹) for optimal yield. However, the finding at Aliero does not support that where 150kg ha⁻¹ was at par with 600kg ha⁻¹. This could be as a result of possible luxury consumption or negative effects at very high rates at specific site. This aligns with caution raised in the background that excessive application of nitrogen can lead to issues like root forking⁸.

Furthermore, spacing had significantly influenced yield of carrot at Jega. The highest yield (10.42 t ha⁻¹) was obtained at plant spaced at 10cm which directly increases plant population per hectare. This result is consistent with the principle for a high crop like carrot, maximizing plant population is often primary driver of high yield per unit area, provided other resources are not limited^{12, 10}. However, the wider spacing (15-25cm) at Jega produced roots with significantly higher dry weight. The tradeoff between the number of roots and the size of individual roots is a classic response to plant population density while 10cm spacing gave the highest bulk yield.

At Aliero, spacing had no significant effect on yield. This could be due to the specific soil conditions at Aliero, where another factor (perhaps water availability or inherent soil fertility) was more limiting than light or space, thereby hindering the effect of Spacing.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, application of NPK (15:15:15) is key for enhancing the growth and yield of carrot in Sudan Savanna Zone of Kebbi State, Nigeria as the soils are deficient in essential nutrients. The optimal

NPK rate is location specific. A rate of 600 kg ha⁻¹ is ideal for Jega for optimizing yield while 150 kg ha⁻¹ for Aliero which maybe efficient and cost effective. Plant spacing influenced yield through plant population density with a closer spacing of 10cm giving the higher yield per hectare while 15-20cm gave a larger individual roots.

6 Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, application of 600 kg ha⁻¹ couple with a 10cm spacing is recommended for maximizing carrot yield in the Sudan Savanna Zone of Kebbi State, Nigeria

Further studies

1. Integrated nutrient management study should be carried out so as to reduce the reliance on high rates of inorganic fertilizer which is costly and may not be sustainable for soil health in the long term.
2. Testing other carrot varieties cope with NPK rates and spacing combination so as to identify genotype-by-environment interactions.

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